

Supporting Information for

On-surface Synthesis of Porous Carbon

Nanoribbons from Polymer Chains

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Figure S1. 1,3,5-Tris(3-bromophenyl)benzene (*m*TBPB) evaporated at room temperature (300 K) on Ag(111). (a) Large-scale overview scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) image of a halogen-bonded porous network of C_{3h} -*m*TBPB conformers in the center (white dashed line) that is surrounded by unordered *m*TBPB clusters. (b) Detailed STM image of a disordered *m*TBPB cluster. Arrows are pointing to a cleaved bromine (blue), to a C_S -*m*TBPB conformer (green) and a C_{3h} -*m*TBPB conformer (black). (c)-(d) Detailed STM images of both homochiral domains with anticlockwise handedness (*L*-domain) in (c) and clockwise handedness (*D*-domain) in (d). We note, that vacancies in the self-assembled networks allow to unambiguously identify single molecules and their handedness. STM Parameters: (a) 1.5 V, 20 pA, (b) 50 mV, 150 pA, (c) 100 mV, 150 pA, (d) 100 mV, 50 pA.

Figure S2. Structure of the halogen-bonded network after evaporation of *m*TBPB at room temperature (300 K) on Ag(111). (a) Overlay of the tentative model for the halogen-bonded network of *m*TBPB on the STM image shown in Fig. 1b in the main text. (b) High-resolution image obtained with a functionalized tip, where the bromines are visible in the halogen-bonded *m*TBPB networks. This STM image allows for measuring the Br-Br bond distance (0.45 ± 0.03 nm). The trimeric X_3 -synthon among three neighboring bromines is highlighted exemplarily by the black triangle. STM Parameters: (a) 100 mV, 50 pA, frame size: 7.5×7.5 nm², (b) 100 mV, 50 pA.

Figure S3. STM images of organometallic chains with loops and ring-like structures induced by annealing of *m*TBPB on Ag(111) at 350 K. (a) In the large-scale overview image the chain-like and ring-like structures, as discussed in the main text, can be clearly distinguished. However, there is no evidence for an ordered self-assembly of the organometallic structures. (b) Potential open-porous organometallic network with twofold Ag-coordination that is built from debrominated C_{3h} -conformers. We note, this network was not observed in the STM experiments on Ag(111). STM Parameters: (a) 400 mV, 50 pA.

Figure S4. STM images showing covalently-linked *m*TBPB chains with periodic nanopores induced by annealing at 410 K on Ag(111). Detailed STM images of both homochiral domains with anticlockwise handedness (*L*-domain) in (a) and clockwise handedness (*D*-domain) in (b). STM Parameters: (a-b) -50 mV, 500 pA.

Figure S5. Different possible models for the self-assembly of the polymer chains consisting out of *trans* and *cis* dimers. The colored dots indicate pockets for the bromine adsorption. The number of surrounding hydrogens is color coded (6 H: green, 4 H blue). The observed closed packed self-assembly (top model) out of *trans* dimers allows more hydrogen pockets per area as the models for the *cis* dimers (middle and bottom model). In the STM images we observed predominantly self-assembled chains that are composed of *trans* dimers.

Figure S6. *Cis*-defect line in a *trans*-chain self-assembly of covalently-linked *mTBPB* chains with periodic nanopores induced by annealing at 550 K on Ag(111). (a) High resolution STM image. (b) Model of the *cis*-defect line. The rows *cis*-dimers are highlighted in green and orange. STM Parameters: (a) -50 mV, 500 pA.

Figure S7. STM overview image of covalently-linked *mTBPB* chains with periodic nanopores. It shows that chains grow (550 K) over monatomic steps of the surface (black arrows), implying that they are robust enough to overcome the potential barrier at the steps. STM Parameters: -1000 mV, 150 pA.

Figure S8. (a) Partially polymerized ring-like structures obtained after annealing at 410 K on Ag(111) with overlaid model (b)-(c) Sequence of STM images of the partially polymerized ring-like structures after annealing at 550 K, where the three bright protrusions in the center of a ring structure are proposed to originate from the out-of-plane rotation of single *m*-phenylene units. The protruding phenylene units can be manipulated via the tip by scanning at close distance (arrows denote the scan direction), which leads to a concurrent flipping of neighboring phenylene units. Once a protruding phenylene unit is planarized, a neighboring one rotates out of the plane. This clearly indicates that the out-of-plane rotation provides a mean for relief of ring strain, which arises from repulsion between nearby H atoms. (d) The same rotation can also be observed in strongly bended chains grown at 410 K (see arrow). (e) While at 550 K most of the ring-like structures have three protruding moieties, we observe after annealing at higher temperatures (630 K) fully planarized ring-like structures or ring-like structures with one protruding *m*-phenylene moiety, as shown in (e). STM Parameters: (a)-(d) -50 mV, 500 pA, (e) -50 mV, 150 pA.

Figure S9. *Cis-Trans*-isomerization of a *m*TBPB dimer unit (highlighted in red) in the polymer chains via flipping of a *m*-phenylene unit (highlighted in blue). We note that the phenylene units are simplified by hexagons.